

Supplementary Table S5: Associations between 78 SNPs in ERCC4 and ERCC5 and 22 cancers risk based on each SNP extracted from one data source.

Ref ID	First author, Year	cancer site	Country/region	ethnicity	Study design	Case	control	sample size	Gene	variant	Allelic ^a	OR (95%CI)	FPRP ^b
2	Zhu,J, 2018	Kidney	China	Asian	HBCCS	139	531	670	ERCC4	rs2276466 (C>G)	G vs C	1.083 (0.785-1.494)	
2	Zhu,J, 2018	Kidney	China	Asian	HBCCS	142	531	673	ERCC5	rs2094258 (C>T)	T vs C	1.399 (1.032-1.898)	0.467
2	Zhu,J, 2018	Kidney	China	Asian	HBCCS	142	531	673	ERCC5	rs751402 (A>G)	G vs A	1.051 (0.783-1.411)	
2	Zhu,J, 2018	Kidney	China	Asian	HBCCS	142	531	673	ERCC5	rs2296147 (T>C)	C vs T	1.139 (0.811-1.600)	
2	Zhu,J, 2018	Kidney	China	Asian	HBCCS	142	531	673	ERCC5	rs1047768 (T>C)	C vs T	1.141 (0.887-1.467)	
2	Zhu,J, 2018	Kidney	China	Asian	HBCCS	142	531	673	ERCC5	rs873601 (G>A)	A vs G	1.142 (0.914-1.425)	
3	Lawania,S, 2018	Lung	India	Asian	HBCCS	370	377	747	ERCC4	rs316028 (C>T)	T vs C	1.460 (1.003-2.126)	0.623
3	Lawania,S, 2018	Lung	India	Asian	HBCCS	370	370	740	ERCC4	rs254942 (G>A)	A vs G	0.974 (0.801-1.184)	
5	Zhao,Z, 2018	Ovary	China	Asian	HBCCS	87	356	443	ERCC4	rs2276466 (C>G)	G vs C	0.986 (0.870-1.117)	
5	Zhao,Z, 2018	Ovary	China	Asian	HBCCS	89	356	445	ERCC5	rs2094258 (C>T)	T vs C	1.133 (0.907-1.414)	
5	Zhao,Z, 2018	Ovary	China	Asian	HBCCS	89	356	445	ERCC5	rs751402 (A>G)	G vs A	0.884 (0.648-1.206)	
5	Zhao,Z, 2018	Ovary	China	Asian	HBCCS	89	356	445	ERCC5	rs2296147 (T>C)	C vs T	0.919 (0.736-1.148)	
5	Zhao,Z, 2018	Ovary	China	Asian	HBCCS	89	356	445	ERCC5	rs1047768 (T>C)	C vs T	1.090 (0.872-1.362)	
5	Zhao,Z, 2018	Ovary	China	Asian	HBCCS	89	356	445	ERCC5	rs873601 (G>A)	A vs G	0.951 (0.751-1.203)	
7	Campo,R, 2017	Stomach	Spain	Caucasian	CCS	117	602	719	ERCC4	rs2238463 (C>G)	G vs C	0.789 (0.397-1.569)	
7	Campo,R, 2017	Stomach	Spain	Caucasian	CCS	116	601	717	ERCC4	rs3136038 (C>T)	T vs C	0.667 (0.179-2.491)	
7	Campo,R, 2017	Stomach	Spain	Caucasian	CCS	595	594	1189	ERCC4	rs1800067 (G>A)	A vs G	1.020 (0.817-1.274)	
8	Dziki,L, 2017	Colorectum	Poland	Caucasian	CCS	309	304	613	ERCC4	49364215 (Arg>S)	Ser vs Arg	1.012 (0.828-1.236)	
9	Wang,M, 2017	Prostate	China	Asian	CCS	1004	1055	2059	ERCC4	rs2276464 (G>C)	C vs G	0.789 (0.642-0.971)	0.337
9	Wang,M, 2017	Prostate	China	Asian	CCS	1004	1055	2059	ERCC5	rs751402 (A>G)	G vs A	1.009 (0.781-1.303)	
11	Ying,M,F, 2016	Pancreas	China	Asian	CCS	195	254	449	ERCC5	rs2094258 (C>T)	T vs C	1.224 (0.895-1.672)	
13	Zhao,F, 2015	Pancreas	China	Asian	HBCCS	246	246	492	ERCC5	rs873601 (G>A)	A vs G	0.879 (0.751-1.029)	
14	Kabzinski,J, 2015	Colorectum	Poland	Caucasian	CCS	146	149	295	ERCC4	rs1799801 (T>C)	C vs T	1.024 (0.799-1.311)	
16	Paszowska S,K, 2015	Colorectum	Poland	Caucasian	PBCCS	752	1263	2015	ERCC4	rs762521 (G>A)	A vs G	0.953 (0.625-1.453)	
16	Paszowska S,K, 2015	Colorectum	Poland	Caucasian	PBCCS	651	649	1300	ERCC5	rs4150360 (C>T)	T vs C	0.892 (0.679-1.173)	
19	Slojewski,M, 2014	Prostate	Poland	Caucasian	CCS	531	772	1303	ERCC4	rs762521 (G>A)	A vs G	0.925 (0.740-1.157)	
19	Mirecka A, 2014	Prostate	Poland	Caucasian	CCS	615	783	1398	ERCC5	rs1047769 (A>G)	G vs A	0.947 (0.724-1.238)	
21	Pei,X,H, 2014	Breast	China	Asian	HBCCS	417	417	834	ERCC4	rs1799797 (T>C)	C vs T	1.060 (0.848-1.324)	
21	Pei,X,H, 2014	Breast	China	Asian	HBCCS	417	417	834	ERCC4	rs2276466 (C>A)	A vs C	1.389 (1.126-1.714)	0.052
22	Liu,Y, 2014	Esophagus	China	Asian	CCS	1524	1524	3048	ERCC4	rs3136038 (C>T)	T vs C	1.024 (0.833-1.260)	
22	Liu,Y, 2014	Esophagus	China	Asian	CCS	1524	1524	3048	ERCC4	rs254942 (G>A)	A vs G	1.408 (0.830-2.388)	
25	Li,X, 2014	Laryngeal	China	Asian	HBCCS	210	210	420	ERCC4	rs2276466 (C>G)	G vs C	0.698 (0.548-0.887)	0.088
28	Santos,L,S, 2013	Thyroid	Portugal	Caucasian	HBCCS	102	210	312	ERCC4	rs1800067 (G>A)	A vs G	0.709 (0.549-0.916)	0.192
29	Wang,X,F, 2013	Brain	China	Asian	CCS	330	652	982	ERCC4	rs1799797 (T>A)	A vs T	0.740 (0.583-0.940)	0.244
29	Wang,X,F, 2013	Brain	China	Asian	CCS	331	684	1015	ERCC4	rs3743538 (G>T)	T vs G	0.738 (0.582-0.935)	0.220
29	Wang,X,F, 2013	Brain	China	Asian	CCS	330	652	982	ERCC4	rs2276466 (G>A)	A vs C	0.757 (0.598-0.957)	0.307
30	Yang,Z, 2013	Breast	China	Asian	HBCCS	461	504	965	ERCC4	rs6498486 (A>C)	C vs A	0.744 (0.586-0.945)	0.264
30	Yang,Z, 2013	Breast	China	Asian	HBCCS	461	504	965	ERCC4	rs2276466 (C>G)	G vs C	0.763 (0.602-0.966)	0.350
31	Wyss,A,B, 2013	Head and Neck	USA	African	PBCCS	305	251	556	ERCC4	rs3136085 (G>C)	C vs G	0.754 (0.587-0.969)	0.385
31	Wyss,A,B, 2013	Head and Neck	USA	African	PBCCS	305	251	556	ERCC4	rs3136091 (C>G)	G vs C	0.788 (0.620-1.000)	
31	Wyss,A,B, 2013	Head and Neck	USA	African	PBCCS	305	251	556	ERCC4	rs3136130 (G>T)	T vs G	0.837 (0.667-1.049)	
31	Wyss,A,B, 2013	Head and Neck	USA	African	PBCCS	305	251	556	ERCC4	rs2020955 (T>C)	C vs T	0.976 (0.706-1.349)	
32	Zhang,J,S, 2013	Stomach	China	Asian	HBCCS	331	355	686	ERCC4	rs1800067 (G>C)	C vs G	1.217 (1.052-1.407)	0.132
32	Zhang,J,S, 2013	Stomach	China	Asian	HBCCS	331	355	686	ERCC4	rs2276466 (C>A)	A vs C	0.825 (0.735-0.926)	0.020
34	Chu,H, 2013	Stomach	China	Asian	HBCCS	350	468	818	ERCC4	rs31870 (A>G)	G vs A	0.980 (0.865-1.110)	
35	Paszowska S,K, 2013	Skin	Poland	Caucasian	CCS	626	1263	1889	ERCC4	rs762521 (G>A)	A vs G	0.904 (0.736-1.109)	
35	Paszowska S,K, 2013	Skin	Poland	Caucasian	CCS	633	1330	1963	ERCC5	rs1047768 (T>C)	C vs T	0.910 (0.648-1.277)	
35	Paszowska S,K, 2013	Skin	Poland	Caucasian	CCS	650	1356	2006	ERCC5	rs1047769 (A>G)	G vs A	1.145 (0.847-1.546)	
35	Paszowska S,K, 2013	Skin	Poland	Caucasian	CCS	636	1332	1968	ERCC5	rs2227869 (G>C)	C vs G	0.979 (0.753-1.272)	
35	Paszowska S,K, 2013	Skin	Poland	Caucasian	CCS	519	649	1168	ERCC5	rs4150360 (C>T)	T vs C	1.049 (0.811-1.355)	
37	Yu,H, 2012	Head and Neck	USA	Caucasian	HBCCS	1040	1046	2086	ERCC4	rs2276466 (C>G)	G vs C	1.272 (1.212-7.635)	
38	Sakoda,L,C, 2012	Lung	USA	Caucasian	CCS	744	1477	2221	ERCC4	rs1799797 (T>A)	A vs T	1.044 (0.782-1.394)	
38	Sakoda,L,C, 2012	Lung	USA	Caucasian	CCS	744	1477	2221	ERCC4	rs3136166 (T>G)	G vs T	0.773 (0.514-1.161)	
38	Sakoda,L,C, 2012	Lung	USA	Caucasian	CCS	743	1474	2217	ERCC5	rs7325708 (C>G)	G vs C	1.101 (0.796-1.524)	
38	Sakoda,L,C, 2012	Lung	USA	Caucasian	CCS	740	1471	2211	ERCC5	rs1047769 (A>G)	G vs A	1.022 (0.869-1.201)	
38	Sakoda,L,C, 2012	Lung	USA	Caucasian	CCS	742	1475	2217	ERCC5	rs4150351 (A>C)	C vs A	0.821 (0.581-1.161)	
38	Sakoda,L,C, 2012	Lung	USA	Caucasian	CCS	742	1475	2217	ERCC5	rs4150355 (C>T)	T vs C	1.063 (0.902-1.252)	
38	Sakoda,L,C, 2012	Lung	USA	Caucasian	CCS	744	1474	2218	ERCC5	rs4150386 (A>C)	C vs A	0.990 (0.871-1.127)	
38	Sakoda,L,C, 2012	Lung	USA	Caucasian	CCS	741	1476	2217	ERCC5	rs4150393 (A>G)	G vs A	0.819 (0.673-0.997)	0.475
39	Zhou,R,M, 2012	Esophagus	China	Asian	CCS	789	778	1167	ERCC4	rs6498486 (A>C)	C vs A	1.028 (0.806-1.313)	
40	Doherty,J,A, 2011	uterus	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	713	717	1430	ERCC4	rs3136064 (C>T)	T vs C	1.088 (0.798-1.483)	
40	Doherty,J,A, 2011	uterus	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	708	715	1423	ERCC4	rs3136215 (T>C)	C vs T	0.942 (0.825-1.077)	
40	Doherty,J,A, 2011	uterus	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	715	710	1425	ERCC5	rs2296147 (T>C)	C vs T	1.118 (0.793-1.576)	
40	Doherty,J,A, 2011	uterus	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	680	699	1379	ERCC5	rs4150261 (G>A)	A vs G	0.982 (0.700-1.378)	
40	Doherty,J,A, 2011	uterus	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	681	700	1381	ERCC5	rs4150276 (T>A)	A vs T	1.053 (0.702-1.581)	
40	Doherty,J,A, 2011	uterus	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	702	679	1381	ERCC5	rs3818356 (G>A)	A vs G	0.825 (0.567-1.201)	
40	Doherty,J,A, 2011	uterus	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	702	681	1383	ERCC5	rs4150351 (A>C)	C vs A	1.164 (0.838-1.617)	
40	Doherty,J,A, 2011	uterus	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	702	680	1382	ERCC5	rs4150355 (C>T)	T vs C	1.023 (0.770-1.359)	
40	Doherty,J,A, 2011	uterus	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	726	722	1448	ERCC5	rs4150375 (A>G)	G vs A	1.226 (0.939-1.602)	
40	Doherty,J,A, 2011	uterus	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	702	680	1382	ERCC5	rs4150383 (G>A)	A vs G	0.977 (0.858-1.113)	
40	Doherty,J,A, 2011	uterus	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	664	646	1310	ERCC5	rs4150386 (A>C)	C vs A	0.935 (0.614-1.423)	
40	Doherty,J,A, 2011	uterus	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	702	681	1383	ERCC5	rs4150393 (A>G)	G vs A	0.736 (0.533-1.015)	
44	Rajaraman,P, 2010	Brain	USA	Caucasian	HBCCS	124	471	595	ERCC4	rs1800067 (G>A)	A vs G	1.714 (1.090-2.696)	0.571
44	Rajaraman,P, 2010	Brain	USA	Caucasian	HBCCS	65	471	536	ERCC4	rs1800067 (G>A)	A vs G	0.709 (0.319-1.577)	
45	Wang,M, 2010	Bladder	China	Asian	HBCCS	234	250	484	ERCC4	rs31870 (A>G)	G vs A	1.145 (0.8491-1.546)	
45	Wang,M, 2010	Bladder	China	Asian	HBCCS	130	150	280	ERCC4	rs6498486 (A>C)	C vs A	0.651 (0.108-3.911)	
47	Abbasi,R, 2009	Laryngeal	Germany	Caucasian	PBCCS	248	647	895	ERCC4	rs1800067 (G>A)	A vs G	1.095 (0.799-1.500)	
48	Pan,J, 2009	Esophagus	USA	Caucasian	CCS	384	453	837	ERCC4	rs2020955 (T>C)	C vs T	1.276 (0.883-1.843)	
48	Pan,J, 2009	Esophagus	USA	Caucasian	CCS	382	457	839	ERCC5	rs17655 (G>C)	C vs G	0.737 (0.477-1.139)	
50	Rajaraman,P, 2008	Breast	USA	Caucasian	CCS	821	1071	1892	ERCC4	rs1800124 (A>G)	G vs A	0.943 (0.702-1.267)	
51	Lin,J, 2008	Kidney	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	319	326	645	ERCC4	rs2020955 (T>C)	C vs T	1.000 (0.741-1.349)	
51	Lin,J, 2008	Kidney	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	323	335	658	ERCC5	rs17655 (G>C)	C vs G	0.937 (0.818-1.073)	
53	Han,J, 2009	Breast	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	238	473	711	ERCC4	rs11648736 (G>A)	A vs G	1.017 (0.752-1.375)	
53	Han,J, 2009	Breast	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	238	475	713	ERCC4	rs4781560 (T>C)	C vs T	1.022 (0.822-1.270)	
53	Han,J, 2009	Breast	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	235	471	706	ERCC4	rs3136130 (G>T)	T vs G	0.907 (0.713-1.153)	
53	Han,J, 2009	Breast	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	236	472	708	ERCC4	rs11646332 (C>A)	A vs C	1.049 (0.912-1.206)	
53	Han,J, 2009	Breast	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	237	475	712	ERCC4	rs11649492 (G>A/C)	A/C vs G	0.998 (0.875-1.138)	
53	Han,J, 2009	Breast	USA	Caucasian	PBCCS	235	473	708	ERCC4	rs31			